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GEOLOGICAL AND MINERALOGICAL SUBSTANTIATION OF THE KHODJADIK AREA

Panjiyev Hikmat Ahadillayevich

Teacher

*Karshi State Technical University,
Karshi, Uzbekistan,*

E-mail: hikmat.panjiyev02@mail.ru

Musallamov Zuhridin Xusniddin o'g'li

Student

*Karshi State Technical University,
Karshi, Uzbekistan,*

E-mail: zuhridin.musallamov00@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The need for elements of noble and rare metals is increasing every year, therefore, the development of criteria for the search, exploration, and forecasting of mineral deposits in the country, the effective organization of geological exploration work, and the modern scientific substantiation of rock formation and ore formation are of paramount importance in exploration and forecasting. The results of petrophysical studies, stratigraphic and geological conditions of the Rudny deposit serve as the most important information source.

Keywords: *Khodzhadik, Chakylkalyan, skarn, scheelite, quartz-sericite, quartz-plagioclase and quartz sandstones, quartzites, mica-carbon-quartz, carbon-mica, hundred-quartz shale and sandstone.*

АННОТАЦИЯ

Еже годно растет потребности на элементы благородные и редкие металлы, с связи с этим разработки критерии поиска, разведки и прогнозирования месторождений полезных ископаемых стране, эффективно организовать геолого-разведочный работ, современно научной обоснование формирования горных пород и рудообразование, разведка-прогнозировании является важнее значения. Важнейшие информационно источником служат результате петрофизический исследование стратиграфический и геологические условия Рудни месторождение.

Ключевые слова: *Ходжадик, Чахылкалян, скарн, шеелит, кварц-серицит, кварц-плагиоклаз и кварцевые песчаники, кварциты, слюда-углеродисто-кварцевый, углеродисто-слюди, сто-кварцевый сланец и песчаник.*

INTRODUCTION

The Khodjadik ore deposit belongs to the northern Chakilkalyan mineralogical zone (part of the Zarafshan-Aloy megazone), which is characterized by structures associated with the collisional tectonic stage, such as olistostrome complexes and strike-slip faults. The northeastern regions are distinguished by structures including dike complexes of alkaline basaltoids and lamprophyres. The mineralogical profile of the area is defined by gold-tungsten mineralization.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODS

The Khodjadik ore deposit is located in the northern sector of the Chakilkalyan megablock, which hosts several skarn and skarnoid-type formations. Scheelite mineralization in the skarns of the Chakilkalyan mountains was first discovered in 1945. Since then, work has been carried out to assess the potential of known tungsten sites and identify new prospective areas.

The Khodjadik ore deposit contributed to the development of ideas regarding rock identification, stratigraphic features of the area, and the material composition of ores.

In 1967–68, in the northern part of the Chakilkalyan megablock, particularly in the Khodjadik-Kamangaron-Yakhton section, a complex of geological and geophysical works, including geochemical geodesy, was conducted on a 1:10,000 scale (Jizzakh GGG), covering an area of 100 km². This work, led by P. F. Yegorov and N. Giyasov, aimed to identify schlicht tests, lithochemical search for primary aureoles, magnetometry, the VP method, and to analyze lithological-stratigraphic and geophysical aureoles. Additional geological surveys were conducted in 1968, in collaboration with other parties. The exploration and survey work was carried out by the Chakilkalyan QRG group of the Zarafshan expedition.

RESULTS

In the Khodjadik ore deposit area, Paleozoic and thin Cenozoic rocks with complex structural formations and metamorphosed sedimentary rocks were identified. Ushakov V.N. divided the Paleozoic deposits into four main geological units: volcanogenic-terrigenous; volcanogenic-terrigenous-carbonate; carbonate; and terrigenous-silica-carbonate suites.

The Ordovician Paleozoic (O₂₋₃) Shakhriomon suite includes volcanogenic-terrigenous formations. The distribution of Paleozoic rocks in the Chakilkalyan

mountains falls into three types: (1) in the southern part of the lower zone, volcanic rocks make up to 10-15% of clastic rocks; (2) in the northern subzone, terrigenous rocks dominate due to physical and chemical processes; and (3) in the central part, terrigenous rocks are extensively developed. These layers consist of shales, siltstones, sandstones, gravelites, conglomerates, volcanic rocks, and lenses of clayey limestones. The rock composition features abundant chlorite or sericite, while fractured or mixed types show increased quartz.

In the western region, rocks consist of green sandstones and quartz-feldspathoid siltstones rich in quartz and mica. Quartz-sericite shales occur as layers. In the east, quartz-plagioclase and sandstone quartz are found, while plains are dominated by sericite rocks combining quartz-chlorite-sericite shales with siltstone layers. Gravelite, andesite porphyry, and their tuffs appear as thin layers. Terrigenous rocks are micro-grained and veined with quartz. Siltstone and shale sequences form oval-shaped layers containing quartz-plagioclase sandstones up to 450 m thick.

Carboniferous formations include volcanogenic-terrigenous-carbonate, tuff-terrigenous-carbonate, and dacite-liparite rocks from the C1 Shing suite. In the Southern Chakilkalyan Mountains, tuff-terrigenous-carbonate rocks are stratified and categorized into two section types: (a) dominated by pure limestones with thick mixed sandstones; and (b) tuff limestones with diverse physical properties. Tuff-ashtite bodies show uneven carbonate distribution and mixed layers that appear as lenses or ribbons. Quartz gravelly rocks appear in lower layers.

These carbonate rocks exhibit a yellowish-gray color due to pyrite sulfidation and oxidation. Clayey limestones appear in dacite-liparite areas as part of calcareous shales. The C₁¹ dacite-liparite formations form layered sequences, indicating ancient magma activity. Volcanic rocks are often altered or quartzitized and may resemble apovolcanogenic rocks. These formations include quartz and dacite porphyries, their tuffs, and minor andesites. Terrigenous rocks coexist, often stratified and chloritized.

The volcanogenic-terrigenous-carbonate rocks contain carbonate-terrigenous-tuffogenic bodies located in aureoles. Ordovician O₂₋₃ volcanogenic-sedimentary structures lie below Lower Silurian dolomites. These rocks vary in color and texture. In the Khodjadik-Yakton-Okbayjuman tungsten area, the carbonate-terrigenous-tuffaceous layer is diverse and non-typical of the Chakilkalyan Mountains. Green shales and amphibolites dominate, with alternating shales, tuffs, and gravelites. Thickness varies from 20–30 m to 150 m. In the east, the layers transition from terrigenous-volcanogenic to carbonate structures.

Tuff-aluminosilicate rocks appear as thin lenticular limestone-alternating layers. Mineral content in tuff rocks decreases in the Shing suite, while dolomites form in adjacent carbonate layers. Ore zones contain rhyolite tuffs, fragmented sand-clay layers, and shales composed of sericite-quartz, feldspar-sericite-quartz, and chlorite-sericite-quartz. The carbonate-terrigenous-tuff layer is 100 m thick in the northwest and 20–50 m in the southeast.

Carbonate and tuff rock genesis is inferred from mineralogically similar volcanogenic rocks beneath and above limestones. Lower Wenlock Formation limestones in the Chakilkalyan Mountains contain stromatopores, corals, and brachiopods. In Kamangaron, the formation includes tuff-clayey limestones, alkaline tuffs, and dolomites with scheelite mineralization, showing pink color from oxidized pyrite. Thickness ranges from 50–100 m.

In the Yakhton deposit, the formation includes light and dark gray, yellowish-gray fine-grained limestones. Terrigenous and effusive-terrigenous deposits form layers of 10–30 cm. Carbonate analysis shows 5.6–16.4% dolomite. The lenticular layers contain sandstones, shales, and volcanic rocks. Kavarish layers (1–5 mm thick) add microtexture. Effusive-sedimentary rocks are metamorphosed and structurally altered. Layer thickness is 20–100 m.

The eastern Chakilkalyan megablock hosts tungsten mineralization in magmatic clayey-tuffogenic limestones with alkaline effusives up to 250 m thick. These rocks are pink-brown due to oxidized pyrite. Distribution halos contain quartz-feldspar-diopside and potassium-silicate minerals.

The C_{1-2} – D_1 carbonate formation is divided into three parts, visible in vertical sections. The dolomite formation (Kuturak) in zone C_{1-2} includes clayey and porous dolomites (5–25 m thick), overlain by massive bituminous dolomites. These dark gray dolomites are low in organic matter. The formation includes layered dolomites from gray to light gray, with increased silicate content and tremolite in metamorphic zones. The upper layers consist of banded dark and gray dolomites with dolomitic limestone. Thickness ranges from 300–500 m.

The C_2 Koprak limestone-dolomite formation is thinner in the northern Chakilkalyan section (25–50 m) and has higher silica content. It includes dolomitic limestones, uneven gray limestones, and decorative lenticular-nodular dolomitic layers. Above, banded dolomitized limestones include dolomite lenses (up to 5 m).

C_2 limestone-dolomite rocks appear in thin strips with lenticular and striated textures. No sharp boundaries exist. Bituminous dolomitic limestones contain organic matter. Components vary, including reddish or brown terrigenous material and

siliceous concretions. Contact metamorphism causes strong recrystallization. Dolomitic limestones lie consistently with limestone rocks. Total layer thickness: 250 m.

In the D₁ Madmon suite, limestones are massive, thinly striated, and gray. Contacts are indistinct due to carbonaceous variation. Aphanitic types dominate, with rare chalcedony and dendritic forms. These deposits are thicker in the southern Chakilkalyan area. The central part contains shale, clay-carbonate, and lens formations. Rocks are marbled by contact metamorphism. Thickness reaches 450 m.

In the D₁₋₂ Khojakorgon suite, terrigenous-siliceous-carbonate rocks show both conformity and stratigraphic unconformities. The region's tectonics feature shear movement. Most formations are Middle Devonian, but the southern subzone includes Lower Devonian deposits.

The formation consists of dark gray limestone with lenticular and granular inclusions. Clayey shales are interbedded. Siliceous and shale components usually form a few percent but may rise to 40–50% in sections. The red hue of terrigenous materials is notable. Limestones are often dolomitized with fragmental components. Massive limestones sometimes resemble pure limestone. In contact zones, rocks are rapidly marbled. Thickness reaches 500 m.

Cenozoic deposits are widespread in lowland areas, particularly in the Ulus-Jam depression, northern foothills, and Kashkadarya basin. Paleogene, Neogene, and Quaternary formations are identified.

Quaternary deposits (Q) occur along mountain slopes, water bodies, and valleys. They consist of conglomerates, loess, loess-like and clayey soils, gravel, and crushed stone. In mountains, thickness is 30–50 m; in foothills, over 100 m.

CONCLUSION

Laboratory analyses conducted include chemical analysis (714 samples), spectral analysis (1,611 samples), mass spectrometry (ISP) (65 samples), and gold analysis (320 samples).

The Khodjadik ore deposit features folded structures formed by tectonic compression, associated with tungsten mineralization and steep dips. Tungsten ore bodies consist of pyroxene-chalcopyrite-quartz, pyroxene-amphibole-chalcopyrite-quartz, and amphibole-chalcopyrite-quartz skarns. Scheelite, the main tungsten mineral, occurs in three generations, with pyrrhotite as the primary sulfide. Pyrite and chalcopyrite are present in smaller amounts. Total sulfide content in ores does not exceed 2–4%.

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